

Lingulaulax polyedra bloom in the Port of Tomis, Romania

Fig. 1. Map of the bloom location.

The Port of Tomis is situated in the city of Constanța, along the western coast of the Black Sea in Romania (Fig. 1). This marina is popular for both fishing and recreational vessels and often attracts tourists and locals alike. Its semi-enclosed waters, enriched with nutrients

and influenced by human activity, provide conditions that can favour algal blooms.

Aquaculture in the Romanian Black Sea region has not reached its full potential due to environmental constraints and an unclear legislative framework.

However, despite these challenges, there is a growing interest in developing mussel and fish aquaculture, driven by the rising demand for seafood and the potential economic benefits it offers [1].

From October 19 to 28, 2024, an unusual water discoloration was observed in the area. This phenomenon was marked by a reddish-brown tint on the surface waters during the day. At night, the bloom became particularly remarkable; when the water was disturbed, it produced a bright blue bioluminescence (Fig. 2). The phenomenon quickly attracted local attention and was soon reported by the media. Microscopic analysis of water samples revealed the dominance of *Lingulaulax polyedra*, an armoured marine dinoflagellate (Fig. 3). This single-cell organism is commonly found in coastal waters and is known for producing a blue nighttime glow, a phenomenon called bioluminescence. Inside the cells, special organelles called scintillons contain the enzyme luciferase and its substrate luciferin. When the water is disturbed, a chemical reaction is triggered that releases a brief flash of blue light, making the sea sparkle at night. The function of this glow is still debated. Scientists suggest it may serve as a defence mechanism, either startling predators or attracting larger predators to feed

Fig. 2. *Lingulaulax polyedra* bloom during the day (A) and at night (B).

Fig. 3. Micrograph of *Lingulaulax polyedra* from a sample collected on October 21, 2024.

Fig. 4. Cyst of *Lingulaulax polyedra* (=Lingulodinium machaerophorum).

on grazers (the “burglar alarm” theory) [2]. Others believe it could be a stress response, triggered by mechanical or chemical changes in the environment [3–4]. So, the spectacular glow in the Port of Tomis was basically millions of dinoflagellates flashing their tiny “alarm lights” every time the water was disturbed. At the end of a bloom, resistant cysts were formed (Fig. 4), that set-

tle into the sediments until favourable conditions return [5]. Although *L. polyedra* has been previously recorded along the Romanian Black Sea coast, it usually occurs only rarely and at low abundances. However, during this event, densities exceeded 7×10^6 cells·L⁻¹.

Similar occurrences of red tides caused by *L. polyedra* have also been reported elsewhere in the Black Sea.

Notably, these phenomena were observed in Varna Bay (Bulgaria) during the warm months of 1987–1989, 1992 and in 2005, as well as in Odessa Bay (Ukraine) in September–October of 2020 [5].

Lingulaulax polyedra has been linked with the production of various toxins, including yessotoxins and ichthyotoxins, observed in multiple re-

Fig. 5. Bernd Krock, Oana Vlas and Andreea Gigiță collecting sediment samples.

gions worldwide. Despite this potential for toxicity, most red tide occurrences attributed to this species have not been directly linked to harmful effects [6]. Research on yessotoxins has shown significant gill damage in marine species due to epithelial cell degeneration and necrosis [7]. Although their effects on human health are not well understood, recent studies suggest yessotoxins may induce apoptosis in some tumour cell lines; other cardiotoxic and neurological effects were observed. Due to their potential risk to humans, yessotoxins (YTX) are one of the few groups of marine biotoxins regulated in seafood within the European Union. Regulation (EU) No. 786/2013 establishes a maximum permitted level of 3.75 mg YTX eq/kg [8]. However, only four variants are regulated and screened: YTX, 1a-homoYTX, 45-hydroxyYTX and 45-hydroxy-1a-homoYTX [9].

A previous toxin screening conducted in the Black Sea identified several variants of yessotoxins, other than the regulated ones, which most likely have a similar toxicity as YTX, but are not regulated or regularly screened. The low levels detected in previous studies indicate that the risk of acute intoxication in the western Black Sea was minimal [10], but the occurrence of such dense *L. polyedra* blooms like the one reported here may in fact pose a risk for the local seafood commercialization. There is a potential risk that YTX levels in seafood may exceed safe limits. This means that in the worst case, shellfish that are below the regulated YTX levels could carry a higher toxin load that might remain undetected and pose a

risk to consumers. Fortunately, there have been no incidents reported involving fish kills or instances of intoxicated shellfish linked to this bloom.

On June 19, 2025, researchers from the National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa” (NIMRD) and the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) collected sediment samples at the Port of Tomis (Fig. 5). These, along with a net sample that had been refrigerated from October 2024, were sent to the AWI laboratory for detailed analysis to detect cysts and potential toxins, important indicators for environmental health and food safety.

Future studies on this event will be approached in EX-AQUA [11], a Horizon Europe project that strengthens NIMRD’s role as a centre of excellence in marine algae aquaculture. By investigating *L. polyedra* bloom in the Black Sea, researchers are improving knowledge on harmful algal blooms (HABs), their recurrence potential, and toxin risks. In collaboration with AWI, advanced techniques such as cyst isolation, germination, culture establishment, toxin analysis, and genetic confirmation are being applied. These efforts contribute to EX-AQUA’s goals of enhancing HAB monitoring, supporting sustainable aquaculture, and laying the foundation for early warning systems in shellfish harvesting areas.

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Authors

Andreea Cristina Gigică, Oana Vlas & Laura Boicenco, National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa”, Romania

Bernd Krock, Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany

Email corresponding author:
agigica@alpha.rmri.ro

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